
The Sociocultural Context of the Eskaya Tribe: Preserving Heritage Amid Modern Challenges

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to describe the sociocultural practices of the *Eskaya* tribe in Taytay, Duero, Bohol, using ethnographic research and PESTEL analysis. The findings highlight key aspects of the tribe's political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal systems, emphasizing their cultural significance and need for preservation. The Eskaya tribe sustains itself through gardening and farming. It reflects a simple rural lifestyle intertwined with unique cultural practices, including their indigenous language, mathematical numeration, and writing system. The study underscores the critical role of education, policy, and research in safeguarding these cultural elements. Initiatives like the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) program and enhanced training in the Eskayan script are pivotal in promoting cultural awareness. Policy measures are vital for protecting the tribe's ancestral domain and natural resources amid social and environmental changes that threaten traditional values. Ethnographic observations and interviews with teachers, parents, and students revealed the tribe's vibrant social practices, celebrations, and indigenous technological methods in farming. The legal framework provided by the Indigenous Peoples Rights Act (RA 8371) supports their rights and cultural heritage. Ultimately, the study advocates for increased awareness and deeper research to preserve and celebrate the Eskaya tribe's unique identity for future generations.

Keywords: Eskaya tribe, ethnographic research, preservation, sociocultural practices

INTRODUCTION

This research has been derived from my doctoral research, an ethnomathematics and sociocultural study of the Eskaya tribe. Despite not being from the Eskaya tribe, I became fascinated by their unique sociocultural and ethnomathematical practices. This is an initial background and phase one of the systematics review conducted as part of the Dynamic components of Janiola's Ethnolearning Theory.

Culture significantly shapes and influences an individual's way of life, providing a framework of values, beliefs, and practices that define a society. As Panopio (2007) emphasizes, culture is a complex whole, comprising the social heritage and design for living within a community. The continuous changes brought about by the 21st century have posed challenges to the preservation of cultural identities, particularly among indigenous groups. These changes affect societies, cultures, and personalities, as Panopio and Santico-Rolda (2007) highlight.

The Eskaya tribe of Bohol exemplifies this dynamic. As one of the Philippines' indigenous cultural communities, the Eskaya face the challenge of preserving their sociocultural practices amidst increasing globalization and modern influences. Their distinct language, traditional practices, and unique ethnomathematical systems underscore the need for cultural preservation. This study focuses on documenting and analyzing the sociocultural context of the Eskaya tribe through ethnographic methods and PESTEL analysis to explore the impact of political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal factors on their cultural heritage.

Preservation is not only a cultural necessity but also a constitutional mandate in the Philippines. Article XIV, Section 17 of the 1987 Constitution obligates the State to recognize, respect, and protect the rights of indigenous cultural communities. This includes promoting their cultural development and protecting their ancestral lands as stipulated

in Article XII, Section 5. This research aligns with these legal provisions, contributing to the cultural, social, and educational well-being of the Eskaya.

Furthermore, this study addresses gaps in the literature, particularly in the intersection of sociocultural practices and ethnomathematics within indigenous groups. By examining the Eskaya tribe, the research aims to bridge the past and the future, enriching the field of mathematics education through the integration of indigenous practices. The findings are expected to provide valuable insights for curriculum development, enhancing students' understanding and appreciation of their cultural and mathematical roots.

The Eskaya tribe is a small indigenous group located in Bohol, Philippines, with a population of 1,537 distributed across Duero, Pilar, and Guindulman. Their rich culture, including the "Ineskaya" language and traditional practices, remains vulnerable to external influences. As observed in similar studies, such as Cadorna's (2015) research on the Agta in the Sierra Madre, indigenous cultural systems are deeply intertwined with survival needs and natural resource availability. These systems form a foundation for educational practices and cultural preservation efforts, ensuring sustainability amidst technological advancements.

According to Guha and Ismail (2015), social change often challenges traditional societies, altering patterns of interaction and cultural practices. However, these changes also offer opportunities for documentation and preservation before practices are lost. In the context of the Eskaya, their unique syllabary and traditional songs provide a cultural repository that requires urgent study and conservation.

Durkheim's (2017) structural functionalism provides a theoretical lens to understand the Eskaya tribe as a social system composed of interdependent elements. Each component of their culture, from language to rituals, performs specific functions that sustain their society. This perspective is crucial for identifying the sociocultural characteristics of the Eskaya tribe and understanding the implications of external influences on

their traditional ways of life.

Sicat and David (2016) highlight the global significance of indigenous peoples, who number approximately 370 million worldwide and represent a wealth of cultural diversity. In Asia alone, indigenous groups account for 70% of this population. The Eskaya tribe, as part of this global tapestry, contributes to the cultural richness of the Philippines. However, like many indigenous groups, they face challenges in maintaining their distinct identity amidst globalization. This study aims to document their unique sociocultural practices, contributing to broader efforts to protect and promote indigenous heritage.

Ethnomathematics connects cultural practices with mathematical concepts, offering an alternative perspective on traditional education. By exploring the Eskaya tribe's practices, this research seeks to uncover mathematical concepts embedded in their culture, providing insights for curriculum development. Understanding these practices not only enriches mathematics education but also fosters respect for indigenous cultures among students and educators.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative research design, with a specific focus on ethnography, to comprehensively examine the sociocultural context of the Eskaya tribe. Ethnography, rooted in cultural anthropology, allowed the researcher to immerse themselves within the Eskaya community, offering an in-depth understanding of their values, beliefs, and practices. This immersion enabled the researcher to capture the nuances of the tribe's unique way of life, including political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal aspects. Both primary and secondary data sources were utilized, with emphasis on primary data gathered through field interviews, participant observations, surveys, and focus group discussions, supported by secondary data validated through ethnographic fieldwork.

The PESTEL framework was employed as a key analytical tool to analyze the data, providing a systematic evaluation of the

external environment affecting the Eskaya tribe. Originating from strategic planning, PESTEL allowed the researcher to critically examine factors such as governance structures (political), resource-based livelihoods (economic), social relationships and cultural norms (social), adoption of modern technologies (technological), interactions with the natural environment (environmental), and legal protections for Indigenous rights (legal). This comprehensive analysis contextualized the tribe's sociocultural practices within broader external influences, enriching the ethnographic findings.

Additionally, the Outline of Cultural Materials (OCM) coding system was utilized to organize and interpret the ethnographic data systematically. This coding approach categorized key aspects of social life, including history, demography, and ethnomathematical practices, facilitating a deeper understanding of the Eskaya tribe's cultural systems. The researcher's engagement in the daily activities of the community, including attending celebrations, participating in rituals, and observing educational practices, ensured the authenticity of the findings. These integrated methodologies provided a culturally respectful and holistic exploration of the Eskaya tribe, yielding insights into both the internal and external dimensions of their cultural identity.

The study was conducted in Taytay, Duero, Bohol, one of the settlements of the Eskaya tribe, an indigenous group primarily residing in the hinterlands of Duero, Guindulman, Pilar, and Sierra Bullones in Bohol's southeastern interior. The first settlement, established in the early 20th century by Mariano Datahan, was located in Biabas, Guindulman. A second settlement was founded in 1951 in Taytay under the guidance of Fabian Baja, following Datahan's instructions. Over time, the Eskaya tribe expanded to nearby areas, including Canta-ub, Lundag, Tambongan, Cadapdapan, and Fatimah. Taytay served as the focal site for this research due to its historical and cultural significance.

The respondents included five "totoban" teachers, five "estowas" students, and five parents ("sila/nima"), selected

through purposive sampling. The researcher employed various methods, including formal and informal interviews, participant observation, and focus group discussions, to gather rich, contextual data. Immersion in the daily lives of the Eskaya people, eating, attending their Sunday Masses, participating in annual celebrations, and even staying overnight ensured a nuanced understanding of their sociocultural practices. Data collection tools, such as notebooks, video recorders, and other recording devices, were used with prior consent to uphold ethical standards. Ethical principles were strictly maintained throughout the study, including respect for cultural practices, ensuring anonymity, and protecting the dignity and well-being of all participants. Permission to conduct the study was obtained from relevant stakeholders, including the Eskaya chieftain, the National Commission on Indigenous Peoples (NCIP), and the Department of Education (DepEd).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results and discussion describe the sociocultural practices of the *Eskaya* tribe through a PESTEL (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, Legal) analysis. The political system of the Eskaya tribe includes their ancestral domain, population, policies, and the structures of tribal leadership. The tribe has a population of 10,070 people residing in 18 barangays in Bohol, with 2,104 households in four barangays of the ancestral domain. In Taytay, Duero, all 388 males and 338 females belong to the Eskaya tribe. The Tribal Council is the most important institution. However, it shares jurisdiction with the Barangay Council, leading to defined roles to avoid overlap.

Each barangay has a Tribal Council led by a Chieftain, chosen by the current Chieftain based on birthright. The tribe is divided into 12 groups called "HUNGOS," each electing a leader either by appointment or vote. The Chieftain, with the Tribal Council, administers cultural affairs, including the development and preservation of traditions. The Chieftain also resolves disputes; if unable, the Barangay Captain assists. The tribe

follows customary laws to maintain peace, order, and justice, which need codification to support the better implementation of state policies. Key regulations include prohibitions against gambling, drunkenness, indecent behavior, and stealing.

Additionally, there are rules against idleness, speaking indecently, excessive behavior, and disrespect. Community conduct emphasizes respect for elders, parents, and leaders, and adherence to these regulations ensures harmony. Religious observance is crucial, with Sundays designated for rest and church activities. Women's attire is regulated, and there are specific rules about children's behavior, including prohibiting unproductive games. Members of the community are expected to follow the Constitution and the tribe's commandments and to honor local traditions over foreign customs. The tribe's governance system is deeply tied to its traditional customs. Still, it requires formal codification for better alignment with state policies.

Figure 1

The Eskaya Tribal Councilors

Economic Aspects of the Eskaya tribe rely on both agricultural and cultural resources for economic sustainability. Known for organic farming, they produce various crops like strawberries, vegetables, and flowers, contributing to tourism

through their Eskaya Museum and local crafts. Their agricultural products, including strawberries, *sayote*, and *yakon*, are sold at competitive prices, offering income opportunities for the tribe. Additionally, the tribe's cultural identity, reflected in their unique language, numerals, and alphabet, is a source of pride and economic opportunity through educational initiatives like their alphabet being incorporated into local school curricula.

The social aspect of the tribe is heavily influenced by its connection to nature and cultural traditions. Key practices such as the Panghingilin Ritual (driving away bad spirits before tree cutting) and wildlife hunting reflect their sustainable approach to resource use. The tribe celebrates both national Filipino holidays and their unique holidays, such as Eskaya Day, which fosters unity and pride. Major festivals include Fiesta and Eskaya Day, where they showcase their cultural heritage. Education is a cornerstone of their society, ensuring that the tribe's culture and history are passed down through generations, supported by their written history and preservation efforts.

Figure 2
The Eskaya Alphabet

Culturally, the tribe has its alphabet, numerals, and unique names for days and months. Their alphabet, based on human body figures, is now part of the elementary curriculum, ensuring

the preservation of their language and culture. Culturally, the Eskaya tribe maintains its indigenous system of alphabets, numerals, and names for days and months. The days of the week are named as follows: Leni (Monday), Mimate (Tuesday), Mibor (Wednesday), Hubir (Thursday), Bini (Friday), Ssnubi (Saturday), and Llongo (Sunday). The months are named Emi-o (January), Hebi-on (February), Maso (March), Kabir (April), Ma-o (May), Hubi (June), Hubi-on (July), Tatu-o (August), Sitibi (September), Oktubi (October), Nobi (November), and Dibi (December). Eskaya numeration system as seen in Table 1:

Table 1
The Eskaya Numeration System

Hindu Arabic Numerals	Counting in Eskaya Dialect	Eskaya symbol	Hindu Arabic Numerals	Counting in Eskaya Dialect	Eskaya symbol
1	Oy				
2	Tre				
3	Coy				
4	Pan				
5	Sing				

The Eskaya alphabet, consisting of 46 letters based on the figures of the human body, is integral to the tribe's cultural identity, as seen in Figure 1. This alphabet, along with their dialect, has been officially incorporated into the elementary school curriculum, sanctioned by the Department of Education (DepEd), to help preserve and sustain their cultural heritage.

The technological aspects of the *Eskaya* tribe maintain traditional farming practices; they have gradually integrated some modern technology. However, they still rely on manual tools and farming techniques such as plows, yokes, and basic gardening implements. Transportation is modernized with motorcycles and communal vehicles. Still, the tribe continues to maintain its traditional agricultural practices, which are rain-dependent. The adoption of technology is slow, with the tribe opting for a balance between preserving their ancestral practices and utilizing modern tools when necessary.

Moreover, the tribe's environmental aspect is their

ancestral land in Duero, Bohol, which offers fertile soil and a climate conducive to agriculture. Their farming practices prioritize sustainability, using natural resources responsibly. The tribe is known for growing various vegetables, flowers, and strawberries, and they rely on the cooler climate of their region for certain crops, like strawberries, which they uniquely cultivate in Bohol. Environmental stewardship is crucial to their way of life, with traditions like sustainable rattan harvesting and controlled wildlife hunting ensuring that their natural surroundings remain intact for future generations.

The Legal Aspects of the tribe is when they were recognized as an indigenous group under Republic Act No. 8371, also known as "The Indigenous People's Rights Act of 1997". The tribe received official recognition in 1996 with the awarding of a Certificate of Ancestral Domain Claim (CADC) by the President. CADC No. R7-CADC-14 encompasses 3,173 hectares of land in several areas, including Tatay (Duero), Biabas (Guindulman), Lundag (Pilar), Canta-ub (Sierra-Bullones), and Cadapdapan (Candijay). The researcher focused on Tatay, Duero, where 1,537 square meters of land were granted. The community has a population of 633, consisting of 127 households and 143 families, with 333 males and 300 females. Legal recognition has empowered the tribe, though there are still challenges in codifying and formalizing their traditional laws to align more closely with national regulations.

The *Eskaya* tribe's vision is to promote love for their community, preserve their language, and cultivate unity and peace. Their mission focuses on safeguarding the tribe's rights, protecting their land, and preserving their traditions against exploitative forces. The tribe's goal is to cultivate virtues such as respect for God, helpfulness to others, environmental care, and patriotism, as reflected in their motto: "*Mahadlokon sa Ginoo, Matinabangon sa Kauban, Ma-ampingon sa Kinaiyahan, ug Mahigugma-on sa Nasud.*" The history of the *Eskaya* tribe is preserved through "old books" passed down from generation to generation. These books contain legends, some considered myths by historians, but they offer valuable insights into the tribe's origins. One story recounts their arrival in Bohol from Sumatra, where their first leader, Dangko, had twelve children

who settled near Antequera before moving east. According to the tribe's oral history, the Eskaya first settled in Talibon before relocating to Loon and later to the mountainous barangays of Campatud and Cansubayon. After some time, the tribe established a settlement in the lowlands of Antequera, in an area called Panas, where they lived from 600 A.D. to 1600 A.D. during the Spanish regime. They eventually established Barangay Viga as their capital, stretching to the riverside valleys beyond the current Abatan Bridge.

Figure 3

Eskaya Tribe's Vision Statement

The tribe's most legendary leader, Haring Lomod (Tamblot), was both a datu and high priest, with authority comparable to that of the present-day Cardinal of the Roman Catholic Church. His reign began in the early 1600s, and he was the first Boholano to lead a revolt against the Spanish conquistadors in 1621. The conflict was sparked by the Spanish taking a silver church bell, known locally as "Lingganayng Ugis." Further documentation of *Eskaya's* history includes genealogies and letters, such as one written by Mariano Datahan, a key figure in the settlement, to President Manuel Quezon in 1937. The Eskaya settlement at Taytay, Duero, was founded by Fabian Baja in 1951 under Datahan's guidance. Early settlers accessed the area by walking atop a mountain, which led to the name

"Taytay," meaning "trail" or "pathway." This area, which lies on the border of Duero, Guindulman, Pilar, and Sierra Bullones, was once a densely forested region. This analysis provides a comprehensive view of the Eskaya tribe's sociocultural dynamics and governance structures while highlighting their strong connection to tradition and the environment. The tribe's ongoing efforts to balance modernization with cultural preservation and environmental stewardship reflect a resilient and sustainable community.

CONCLUSION

The ethnographic study and PESTEL analysis of the Eskaya tribe provide a comprehensive understanding of the tribe's sociocultural practices and the importance of preserving and enhancing these traditions. The Eskaya tribe's way of life, rooted in agriculture, community rituals, and strong cultural identity, highlights the deep connection between the people and their environment. The tribe's unique language, mathematical numeration, and writing system are remarkable cultural treasures that need to be safeguarded for future generations.

The study implies that education, policy, and research are crucial in the development and preservation of the Eskaya tribe's sociocultural characteristics. Education plays a pivotal role in enabling the tribe members to understand and appreciate their cultural heritage, as well as their role in preserving it. Initiatives like the Mother Tongue-based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) program and the enhancement of the Eskaya script within the Department of Education's curriculum can significantly contribute to the sustainability of their language and traditions. Policy, especially regarding the protection of the tribe's ancestral domain and natural resources, is vital. While social change is inevitable, it should be approached thoughtfully to ensure that it does not erode *Eskaya's* cultural identity and environmental stewardship. Thorough research and a deeper understanding of the tribe's culture and needs are essential before implementing changes, ensuring that the Eskaya people continue to thrive while preserving their heritage.

In conclusion, the Eskaya tribe's cultural practices and way of life are invaluable and must be protected from external threats. Educating future generations and implementing supportive policies will help preserve these traditions, ensuring that the Eskaya tribe remains a strong, self-sustaining community deeply rooted in its history while adapting to the changing world.

RECOMMENDATION

This research is an avenue to preserve and strengthen the Eskaya tribe's cultural heritage; it is essential to enhance culturally responsive education, implement stronger legal protections, and promote sustainable livelihood programs. Integrating the Eskaya language and script into formal education, training educators, and establishing community learning centers will ensure the transmission of traditional knowledge. Policy measures must safeguard ancestral lands and involve the Eskaya people in decision-making processes. Sustainable eco-tourism and agriculture initiatives can provide economic opportunities while protecting cultural traditions. Additionally, continuous research, documentation, and intergenerational dialogues will reinforce cultural identity and community empowerment. These efforts will help the Eskaya tribe thrive while preserving their unique heritage for future generations.

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